

The idea of unidirectional superconductivity

Electric current can generate magnetism. If a permanent magnet is wrapped around a wire, and the magnetic field lines of the magnet rotate around the wire, will the wire generate unidirectional superconductivity?

单向超导想法

电流能产生磁性。如果在电线裹一层永磁体，磁体的磁感应线围着电线旋转，电线不会产生单方向的超导。